

Investigating Time-Scales in Deep Echo State Networks for Natural Language Processing

Corrado Baccheschi^[0009-0002-6500-9578], Alessandro Bondielli^[0000-0003-3426-6643], Alessandro Lenci^[0000-0001-5790-4308], Alessio Micheli^[0000-0001-5764-5238], Lucia Passaro^[0000-0003-4934-5344], Marco Podda^[0000-0003-1497-9515], and Domenico Tortorella^[0000-0003-3910-7713]

Department of Computer Science, University of Pisa,
Largo B. Pontecorvo, 3, 56127 Pisa, Italy
c.baccheschi@studenti.unipi.it, {name.surname}@unipi.it

Abstract. Reservoir Computing (RC) enables efficiently-trained deep Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) by removing the need to train the hierarchy of representations of the input sequences. In this paper, we analyze the performance and the dynamical behavior of RC models, specifically Deep Bidirectional Echo State Networks (Deep-BiESNs), applied to Natural Language Processing (NLP) tasks. We compare the performance of Deep-BiESNs against fully-trained NLP baseline models on six common NLP tasks: three sequence-to-vector tasks for sequence-level classification and three sequence-to-sequence tasks for token-level labeling. Experimental results demonstrate that Deep-BiESNs achieve comparable or superior performance to these baseline models. We then adapt the class activation mapping technique for explainability to analyze the dynamical properties of these deep RC models, highlighting how the hierarchy of representations in Deep-BiESNs layers contributes to forming the class prediction in the different NLP tasks. Investigating time scales in deep RNN layers is highly relevant for NLP because language inherently involves dependencies that occur over various temporal horizons. The findings not only underscore the potential of Deep ESNs as a competitive and efficient alternative for NLP applications, but also contribute to a deeper understanding of how to effectively model such architectures for addressing other NLP challenges.

Keywords: Echo State Networks · Reservoir Computing · Recurrent Neural Networks · Natural Language Processing · Computational Linguistics.

1 Introduction

Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) [7] have certainly represented a key step forward in natural language processing (NLP), as the sequential nature of language demands models capable of capturing contextual dependencies over time. Despite this, traditional RNNs face well-documented challenges — such as vanishing and exploding gradients — which limit their ability to capture long-term

dependencies [1]. In this context, Reservoir Computing (RC) [21,35] has emerged as a state-of-the-art paradigm for designing efficiently trainable RNNs, offering an alternative that emphasizes computational simplicity without compromising predictive performance. The most well-known model within the Reservoir Computing paradigm is the Echo State Network (ESN) [17,18], a form of RNN in which only the final readout layer is trained, while the recurrent part — referred to as the *reservoir* — remains untrained. On one hand, by eliminating the need for training, ESNs avoid the typical challenges faced by traditional RNNs. On the other hand, training is significantly faster and more efficient, as it is limited to the readout layer. The NLP literature has advanced to focusing mostly on Transformer-based architectures, both for discriminative [5] and generative [24,30] tasks. While these models have shown groundbreaking capabilities in modeling text and generalization, they come with the burden of a very high computational cost, even for small-sized ones. Thus, in this work, we ask ourselves whether the key advantages of the RC paradigm, namely efficiency and the advantages of deep reservoir in representing different time-scales [11,12,32], can be effectively leveraged in the context of NLP tasks. We pose the following research questions:

- RQ1** What are the performances of a Deep ESN on NLP classification tasks?
RQ2 Does the model’s dynamical behavior give any indication of effective text modeling?

To answer RQ1, we look at a subset of the classification tasks proposed in [26]. Specifically, we focus on sequence-level classification (e.g., Sentiment Analysis), modeling it as a sequence-to-vector task, and on token-level classification (e.g., POS-tagging), modeling it as a sequence-to-sequence task. We evaluate the performance of a Bidirectional Deep ESN [2] (Deep-BiESN) on three tasks for each category. We restrict our attention to the bidirectional case since, being able to model the context in both directions, it is inherently more expressive; in fact, it is the *de facto* architecture for recurrent models applied to NLP [20]. To answer RQ2, we resort to: (i) analyzing which hyperparameters (in the considered tasks) lead to dynamics that enable best performance; (ii) leveraging Class Activation Mapping (CAM) Scores to understand the importance of each layer in the network for the final classification.

2 Related works

Reservoir Computing (RC) in NLP spans multiple research directions, including speech recognition [12], language modeling, and text classification [27], with additional implications in psycholinguistics and cognitive science. Research in this area typically emphasizes the neurobiological plausibility of RC — particularly Echo State Networks (ESNs) for sentence processing [14,37] — especially when compared to architectures such as RNNs and Transformers. The possibility of using an ESN as a language model is explored in [15], where the authors propose a classical ESN architecture enhanced with additional working memories [22].

Similarly, in [23], an enhanced ESN with a pre-recurrent feature layer and a nonlinear readout is proposed, demonstrating strong performance in next-word prediction. Bidirectional ESN architectures (Deep-BiESNs) have been explored in [29,28], showing accuracy comparable to Bi-LSTMs on the Word Sense Disambiguation (WSD) task, and confirming the ability of Deep-BiESNs to capture richer contextual information. A related study [25] applies both bidirectional and unidirectional ESNs to Named Entity Recognition (NER), finding that Bi-ESNs outperform their unidirectional counterparts — indicating that NER benefits from bidirectional context. Furthermore, in [9] and [10], ESNs are analyzed from a cognitive science perspective. The authors demonstrate that ESNs not only perform well on next-word prediction tasks but also exhibit strong systematicity—i.e., the human ability to use and understand language in a structured and coherent way, generalizing syntactic and semantic rules to novel word combinations [8]. A comparison between an ESN and a fully trained RNN for next-word prediction is presented in [31], where findings confirm that ESNs are sensitive to grammatical patterns, even without explicit training. Recently, given the success of the Transformer architecture, especially the attention mechanism [34], research has moved in two directions: enhancing ESN performance with self-attention mechanisms, and comparing Transformers and ESNs in terms of both performance and training time. For example, in [4], an ESN equipped with a frozen attention mechanism is used for sentiment analysis on the IMDB dataset, achieving accuracy comparable to Bi-LSTM while requiring less training time. In [6], two bidirectional ESN models (Bi-ESNs) are evaluated on the TREC question classification benchmark. Their models demonstrate competitive performance compared to state-of-the-art approaches, especially in terms of training efficiency and number of trainable parameters. Finally, in [33], authors show that ESNs match or even surpass the performance of Transformers (trained from scratch) in capturing syntactic structure.

3 Deep echo state networks

Deep Echo State Network (DeepESN) [11] is an RC model designed within the deep learning framework. Its reservoir architecture is constructed by stacking multiple ESN layers sequentially, where the output of each layer serves as the input for the next. This approach allows DeepESN to encode the input sequence $\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_x}$ as a hierarchy of representations $\mathbf{h}^{(l)}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{N_R}$, $l = 1, \dots, L$, where each layer focuses on a different time scale [32]. The state transition function of a DeepESN layer is

$$\mathbf{h}^{(l)}(t) = (1-a)\mathbf{h}^{(l)}(t-1) + a \tanh\left(\mathbf{W}_{\mathbf{h}}^{(l)}\mathbf{h}^{(l)}(t-1) + \mathbf{W}_{\mathbf{x}}^{(l)}\mathbf{x}^{(l)}(t) + \mathbf{b}^{(l)}\right) \quad (1)$$

where $0 < a \leq 1$ is the leakage constant [16]. The recurrent weights $\mathbf{W}_{\mathbf{h}}^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_R \times N_R}$ are randomly initialized and rescaled to satisfy the echo state property [17], while the input weights $\mathbf{W}_{\mathbf{x}}^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_R \times N_x}$ and bias $\mathbf{b}^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_R}$ are randomly initialized taking into account the input range.

In this work, we focus on a DeepESN [11,12] variant where the layers are made bidirectional (as in [2]) by encoding the input sequence in both forward and backward temporal directions with two different ESNs. Hereafter, this variant is termed Deep-BiESN. More precisely, the forward and backward directions are encoded as $\vec{\mathbf{h}}^{(l)}(t)$, $\overleftarrow{\mathbf{h}}^{(l)}(t)$, with their concatenation $\bar{\mathbf{h}}^{(l)}(t) = [\vec{\mathbf{h}}^{(l)}(t) \overleftarrow{\mathbf{h}}^{(l)}(t)]$ serving as the overall embedding of time-step t in layer l . In this case, the input to layer $l > 1$ is $\mathbf{x}^{(l)}(t) = \bar{\mathbf{h}}^{(l-1)}(t)$. In sequence-to-vector tasks, we encode the whole sequence via mean-state mapping $\mathbf{H}^{(l)} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=1}^T \bar{\mathbf{h}}^{(l)}(t)$. For downstream tasks, we train a linear readout $\hat{\mathbf{y}} = \mathbf{W}_{\circ} \mathbf{h} + \mathbf{b}_{\circ}$ by closed-form ridge regression [38], either on the concatenation of all layer embeddings or on the last layer representation.

4 Experiments

In this Section, we detail our experimental setup to answer RQ1 and present the results comparing Deep-BiESN with fully-trained NLP baseline models.

4.1 Experimental setup

Our experiments involve applying a Deep-BiESN to several NLP classification tasks. As our source of data, we follow [19] and consider a subset of the tasks and dataset proposed in [26]. Specifically, we focus on three sequence-level classification tasks, namely *Sentence Sentiment*, *Subjectivity*, and *Document Sentiment Classification*, and three token-level classification tasks, namely *Part-of-Speech (POS) Tagging*, *Named Entity Recognition (NER)*, and *Chunking*. We chose these tasks as they are relatively common in the NLP literature, and encompass a relatively wide array of characteristics, from the number of output classes to the linguistic features typically learned to solve the tasks, that make our experiments more robust. For the three sequence-level tasks, we evaluated our models using accuracy, whereas for token-level POS, NER, and Chunking, we used the weighted F1-score as the evaluation metric.

As inputs to the Deep-BiESN, we feed each data point as a sequence of token embeddings. As embedding model we use 300-dimensional pre-trained FastText word embeddings [3]. We chose to use FastText embeddings rather than other methods to maintain continuity with results presented in [19], that serve as our baseline. In the case of sequence-level classification tasks, mean-state mapping is applied to obtain the global sequence embedding. For token-level classification tasks, the output sequence from the model (excluding the padding) is reshaped to be suitable for the readout. Following [38], a closed-form, efficient ridge regression is used as the final readout, enabling batch processing for computationally intensive tasks. As for the model selection, we applied the *hold-out* method, reserving between 10% and 25% of the data for validation and following the split in [26]. We employed an exhaustive grid search, allowing us to explore every possible combination of hyper-parameters. To obtain the desired spectral radius ρ and rescale the recurrent matrix $\mathbf{W}_{\mathbf{h}}$, we use the fast initialization approach

Table 1: Comparison of fully-trained NLP baselines [19] and Deep-BiESN

Task	Baseline model	Baseline score	Deep-BiESN score
Document Sentiment	LSTM	0.761 ± 0.008	0.841 ± 0.002
Sentence Sentiment	CNN	0.782 ± 0.004	0.774 ± 0.002
Subjectivity	Mean Embedding LR	0.910 ± 0.002	0.932 ± 0.001
POS Tagging	Sliding Window LR	0.904 ± 0.001	0.894 ± 0.001
NER	Sliding Window LR	0.942 ± 0.001	0.939 ± 0.001
Chunking	Sliding Window LR	0.905 ± 0.001	0.916 ± 0.001

introduced in [13]. Other hyperparameters selected include number of reservoir units N_R (from the set $\{1000, 3000, 5000, 10000\}$), number of layers L (from the set $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$), leakage rate a (from the set $\{0.05, 0.1, 0.5, 0.9, 1\}$), whether to use only the last layer or the concatenation of all layers’ states, and the L2 ridge regularization (within the logarithmic range $[10^{-8}, 10^{-5}]$). Results are averaged over 10 random initializations of reservoir weights.

4.2 Results

We report the average and standard deviation of test scores in Table 1 for Deep-BiESN and fully-trained NLP baseline models from [19], which include an LSTM recurrent neural network, a convolutional neural network (CNN), a logistic regression (LR) on mean word embeddings, and LRs on sliding windows of the input sequence. All of them have been trained on the same FastText300 word embeddings for a fair comparison. We observe that Deep-BiESN scores are generally comparable to or better than the baseline results. Deep-BiESNs exhibit also a high stability in performance, as reflected by small standard deviations. For document sentiment classification, we outperform the baseline accuracy of LSTM. Conversely, we achieve comparable performance in sentence sentiment classification, albeit with a marginal decline in accuracy of 0.01. For subjectivity, Deep-BiESN again outperforms the baseline in terms of accuracy. For POS and NER we obtain comparable results to the baseline, while also outperforming the performance for Chunking.

Table 2 reports the hyperparameters obtained via model selection for Deep-BiESN in sequence-level and token-level classification tasks. An initial insight into the memory requirements of different tasks can be obtained by analyzing the values of the leakage parameter a , where smaller values denote longer-lasting influence of previous time-steps. In the sentence sentiment classification task, the optimal leakage is $a = 0.05$. This confirms that this task involves more diffuse and long-range temporal dependencies, as the meaning of a sentence often relies on the accumulation of subtle cues distributed across the input. Surprisingly, document-level sentiment classification, which is arguably a more complex task, does not seem to require such a long-term memory, as indicated by the high optimal leakage value ($a = 0.9$). However, the model selection also favored a

three layers architecture, suggesting that the model may rely on hierarchical abstraction across layers to obtain the required information. Similarly, token-level tasks such as POS tagging, Chunking, and NER favored high leakage values ($a = 0.9$), while at the same time benefiting from deeper architectures with five layers.

5 Analysis

To answer RQ2, we look into the dynamical behavior and information retention of the Deep-BiESN models selected for each NLP task. We do so by characterizing the time-scales of each layer via the respective temporal constants (Sec. 5.1), and by measuring the contribution of each layer to the class prediction (Sec. 5.2).

5.1 Temporal scales

We study the dynamical behavior of the Deep-BiESN architectures selected for each NLP task to investigate the temporal scales of the sequence representations required to address the respective learning tasks. We characterize the properties of these models as dynamical systems by measuring their impulse response as done in [32], i.e. how embeddings $\tilde{\mathbf{h}}(t)$ evolve after the input sequence has been perturbed at time-step t_0 compared to the unperturbed embeddings $\mathbf{h}(t)$. Specifically, we measure the *decay time* τ as the time-steps required for the perturbation $\|\mathbf{h}(t) - \tilde{\mathbf{h}}(t)\|$ to decay below 1% of the peak value after t_0 . We report in Table 3 the average temporal constants measured over 10 random input sequences and Deep-BiESN weights initializations, both for the global state that is fed to the readout classifier, as well as for each of the architecture layers individually. As a general trend, we observe that τ increases from the shallowest to the deeper layers. This is in agreement with the results of [32]: temporal responses become more delayed as information has to propagate through the layers, while state perturbations are more lasting in deeper layers compared to shallower layers.

In the sentence sentiment task, the extremely large temporal constant $\tau \approx 80$ is a consequence of the small leakage value $a = 0.05$. As already observed in

Table 2: Hyperparameters from the Deep-BiESN model selection. (When present, ‘last’ denotes that only the last layer was used as input to the readout.)

Task	Selected hyper-parameters
Document Sentiment	$N_R=5,000, a = 0.9, L = 3$
Subjectivity	$N_R=10,000, a = 0.9, L = 2, \text{ last}$
Sentence Sentiment	$N_R=10,000, a = 0.05, L = 1$
POS Tagging	$N_R = 5,000, a = 0.9, L = 5$
NER	$N_R = 5,000, a = 0.9, L = 5$
Chunking	$N_R = 5,000, a = 0.9, L = 5$

Sec. 4.2, this is an indication that long-range temporal dependencies are required. Regarding other sequence-level tasks, the models for document sentiment and subjectivity classification primarily rely on short-term information, effectively acting like a sliding window over time, while information on the whole sequence is supplied by mean-state mapping. This behavior is evidenced by significantly smaller τ values around 3–4 and shallower architectures. For token-level labeling tasks such as NER and Chunking, the values of τ are similarly low notwithstanding the deeper architectures, a hint of similar temporal dynamics. In contrast, for POS tagging, the influence of the input persists further in time, as evidenced by τ values that are noticeably higher than those observed in the other token-level tasks. From a linguistic perspective, we highlight an interesting aspect. We observe that the τ values for the best configuration for each task actually closely match the span of tokens needed to solve them. For example, Named

Table 3: Average values of temporal constants τ computed across 10 random inputs and weight initializations.

Task	Setting	Layer	Decay time τ
Sentence Sentiment	L=1, $a=0.05$	(global)	79.85 ± 0.35
Subjectivity	L=2, $a=0.9$	global	4.00 ± 0.00
		layer 1	4.50 ± 0.00
		layer 2	4.50 ± 0.00
Document Sentiment	L=3, $a=0.9$	global	3.00 ± 0.00
		layer 1	2.00 ± 0.00
		layer 2	3.00 ± 0.00
		layer 3	3.95 ± 0.15
POS Tagging	L=5, $a=0.9$	global	10.15 ± 0.35
		layer 1	5.00 ± 0.00
		layer 2	5.00 ± 0.00
		layer 3	7.00 ± 0.00
		layer 4	9.55 ± 0.49
		layer 5	12.00 ± 0.00
NER	L=5, $a=0.9$	global	6.00 ± 0.00
		layer 1	3.00 ± 0.00
		layer 2	4.00 ± 0.00
		layer 3	5.00 ± 0.00
		layer 4	6.00 ± 0.00
		layer 5	7.00 ± 0.00
Chunking	L=5, $a=0.9$	global	5.00 ± 0.00
		layer 1	3.00 ± 0.00
		layer 2	3.00 ± 0.00
		layer 3	4.00 ± 0.00
		layer 4	5.00 ± 0.00
		layer 5	6.00 ± 0.00

Entities and Chunks are generally composed of a few tokens; to understand the sentiment of an entire sentence the whole content is typically needed; subjectivity cues often revolve around first person pronouns and construction such as “I think”, “I believe”, etc. We however identify two notable exceptions. First, for POS tagging, most traditional systems leverage local, i.e., word level, features, and a small context window, e.g. the preceding and subsequent tokens, while our best configuration for the task has a slightly larger memory. Second, for Document Sentiment Classification, the best performing configuration has actually a very small memory with respect to how the task is typically handled. We leave analysis of this phenomenon to future works.

5.2 Layer importance

As observed by the temporal constants, each layer in a Deep-BiESN model encodes information on the input sequence on different time-scales. To estimate the contribution of each layer to the final prediction, we apply the Class Activation Mapping (CAM) [36] method to assign importance scores to layers. CAM scores are computed by exploiting the linearity of the readout, decomposing the classifier output $\hat{y}^{(k)}$ of class k into the individual contribution of each layer:

$$\hat{y}^{(k)} = \mathbf{W}_o^{(k)} \mathbf{h} + \mathbf{b}_o^{(k)} = \sum_{l=1}^L \underbrace{\mathbf{w}_o^{(k,l)} \mathbf{h}^{(l)}}_{\text{importance score}} + \mathbf{b}_o \quad (2)$$

The larger is the value $|\mathbf{w}_o^{(k,l)} \mathbf{h}^{(l)}|$, the more relevant is layer l for the prediction of class k .

In Figure 1 we report the average relative importance computed by CAM for the tasks that exploit more than one layer in the readout classifier, namely: document classification, POS, NER and Chunking. Overall, relevant linguistic information tends to concentrate within the first two layers of the Deep-BiESN. From a linguistic perspective, this effect may be partially attributed to the local nature of tasks such as POS tagging, chunking, and NER. It is reasonable to expect that the readout receives sufficient information for accurate predictions, relying only on the layers closer to the input. In particular, for POS, we observe that classes corresponding to singular and plural common nouns (NN, NNS), proper singular nouns (NNP), cardinal numbers (CD), and adverbs (RB) are especially influenced by layer 2. For chunking, we observe a similar trend, with layer 1 also emerging as particularly relevant for classes corresponding to the beginning of a noun phrase (B-NP), the inside of a noun phrase (I-NP), and tokens outside of syntactic structures, such as punctuation (O). Additionally, for NER task classes like B-MISC and B-PER seem to be strongly influenced by layer 2; the former indicates a named entity (NE) related to a person (such as “Harry”) while the latter regards NE that don’t fit into the other categories. All of these mentioned classes for POS, NER and Chunking reflect surface-level grammatical features, which are typically easier to detect and require less hierarchical abstraction, thus supporting the idea that early layers are sufficient to

capture the necessary information for these predictions. Interestingly, a marginal yet non-negligible role of layer 3 can be observed in chunking in classes such as I-ADVP (Inside of Adverbial Phrase) and I-LST (Inside of List Marker). A possible linguistic explanation is unlike noun or verb phrases, the internal tokens of adverbial or list chunks typically require more contextual integration to be correctly identified. Thus, the third layer may act as a refinement stage, aggregating temporal patterns and supporting the resolution of ambiguities that are not fully captured by the lower layers.

6 Conclusions

In this work, we applied bidirectional Deep Echo State Networks (Deep-BiESNs) to six widely adopted NLP benchmarks. The experimental results demonstrate that our models consistently achieved strong performance both on sequence-level and token-level tasks, generally matching or surpassing the results of the fully-trained baseline models proposed in [19]. We have performed an analysis of the dynamical properties of Deep-BiESNs to characterize the temporal scales in the hierarchy of layer representations, revealing how these models encode information over different time horizons. This has enabled us to provide insights into the short- and long-term dependencies required by different NLP tasks, investigating the contribution of each layer to the final prediction via Class Activation Mapping (CAM). The analysis revealed that the depth of the network is related to the linguistic traits of the tasks, with layers close to the input encoding surface-level grammatical features, and deeper layers acting as a refinement over local contextual information. Overall, our research has contributed to a better understanding of how to tailor reservoir configurations for specific NLP tasks, with potential applications also to the improvement of fully-trained deep recurrent models. In future works, we plan to extend the scope of our analysis to more comprehensive and complex NLP tasks, applying the same tools of this work to investigate the dynamical properties of end-to-end trained RNNs.

Acknowledgements Research partly supported by: PNRR - M4C2 - Investimento 1.3, Partenariato Esteso PE0000013-“FAIR - Future Artificial Intelligence Research” - Spoke 1 “Human-centered AI”, funded by the European Commission under the NextGeneration EU programme; the EU EIC project EMERGE (Grant No. 101070918); Project DEEP-GRAPH, funded by the Italian Ministry of University and Research, PRIN 2022 (project code: 2022YLRBTT, CUP: I53C24002440006); Project PAN-HUB, funded by the Italian Ministry of Health (POS 2014–2020, project ID: T4-AN-07, CUP: I53C22001300001).

References

1. Bengio, Y., Frasconi, P., Schmidhuber, J.: Gradient flow in recurrent nets: the difficulty of learning long-term dependencies. *A Field Guide to Dynamical Recurrent Neural Networks* (03 2003)

Fig. 1: Layer importance analysis with CAM-Score for POS, Chunking, NER and document sentiment classification.

2. Bianchi, F.M., Scardapane, S., Løkse, S., Jenssen, R.: Bidirectional deep-readout echo state networks. In: ESANN 2018 proceedings. pp. 425–430 (2018)
3. Bojanowski, P., Grave, E., Joulin, A., Mikolov, T.: Enriching word vectors with subword information. *Transactions of the Association for Computational Linguistics* **5**, 135–146 (2017). https://doi.org/10.1162/tacl_a_00051
4. Cabessa, J., Hernault, H., Kim, H., Lamonato, Y., Levy, Y.Z.: Efficient text classification with echo state networks. In: 2021 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN) (2021)
5. Devlin, J., Chang, M.W., Lee, K., Toutanova, K.: BERT: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding. In: Burstein, J., Doran, C., Solorio, T. (eds.) *Proceedings of the 2019 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies, Volume 1 (Long and Short Papers)*. pp. 4171–4186. Association for Computational Linguistics, Minneapolis, Minnesota (Jun 2019). <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/N19-1423>
6. Di Sarli, D., Gallicchio, C., Micheli, A.: Question Classification with Untrained Recurrent Embeddings, pp. 362–375. *AI*IA 2019 – Advances in Artificial Intelligence (11 2019)*. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-35166-3_26
7. Elman, J.L.: Finding structure in time. *Cognitive Science* **14**(2), 179–211 (1990). https://doi.org/10.1207/s15516709cog1402_1
8. Fodor, J.A., Pylyshyn, Z.W.: Connectionism and cognitive architecture: A critical analysis. *Cognition* **28**(1-2), 3–71 (1988)
9. Frank, S.L.: Strong systematicity in sentence processing by an echo state network. In: Kollias, S.D., Stafylopatis, A., Duch, W., Oja, E. (eds.) *Artificial Neural Networks – ICANN 2006*. pp. 505–514. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg (2006)
10. Frank, S.L., Haselager, W.F.G.: Robust semantic systematicity and distributed representations in a connectionist model of sentence comprehension. In: Miyake, N., Sun, R. (eds.) *Proceedings of the 28th Annual Conference of the Cognitive Science Society*. Erlbaum, Mahwah, NJ (2006), in press
11. Gallicchio, C., Micheli, A., Pedrelli, L.: Deep reservoir computing: A critical experimental analysis. *Neurocomputing* **268**, 87–99 (2017)
12. Gallicchio, C., Micheli, A., Pedrelli, L.: Design of deep echo state networks. *Neural Networks* **108**, 33–47 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neunet.2018.08.002>
13. Gallicchio, C., Micheli, A., Pedrelli, L.: Fast spectral radius initialization for recurrent neural networks. In: Oneto, L., Navarin, N., Sperduti, A., Anguita, D. (eds.) *Recent Advances in Big Data and Deep Learning*, pp. 380–390. Springer International Publishing (2020). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-16841-4_39
14. Hinaut, X., Dominey, P.F.: Real-time parallel processing of grammatical structure in the fronto-striatal system: A recurrent network simulation study using reservoir computing. *PLoS ONE* **8**(2), e52946 (2013), epub 2013 Feb 1
15. Homma, Y., Hagiwara, M.: An echo state network with working memories for probabilistic language modeling. In: Mladenov, V., Koprinkova-Hristova, P., Palm, G., Villa, A.E.P., Appollini, B., Kasabov, N. (eds.) *Artificial Neural Networks and Machine Learning – ICANN 2013*. pp. 595–602. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg (2013)
16. Jaeger, H., Lukoševičius, M., Popovici, D., Siewert, U.: Optimization and applications of echo state networks with leaky-integrator neurons. *Neural Networks* **20**(3), 335–352 (2007)

17. Jaeger, H.: The “echo state” approach to analysing and training recurrent neural networks—with an erratum note. Tech. Rep. 148, German National Research Institute for Computer Science (2001)
18. Jaeger, H., Haas, H.: Harnessing nonlinearity: Predicting chaotic systems and saving energy in wireless communication. *Science* **304**(5667), 78–80 (2004)
19. Lenci, A., Sahlgren, M., Jeuniaux, P., et al.: A comparative evaluation and analysis of three generations of distributional semantic models. *Language Resources and Evaluation* **56**, 1269–1313 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10579-021-09575-z>
20. Li, Q., Peng, H., Li, J., Xia, C., Yang, R., Sun, L., Yu, P.S., He, L.: A survey on text classification: From traditional to deep learning. *ACM Trans. Intell. Syst. Technol.* **13**(2) (Apr 2022). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3495162>, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3495162>
21. Lukoševičius, M., Jaeger, H.: Reservoir computing approaches to recurrent neural network training. *Computer Science Review* **3**(3), 127–149 (2009)
22. Pascanu, R., Jaeger, H.: A neurodynamical model for working memory. *Neural Networks* **24**(2), 199–207 (2011)
23. Rachez, A., Hagiwara, M.: Augmented echo state networks with a feature layer and a nonlinear readout. In: *The 2012 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*. pp. 1–8 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1109/IJCNN.2012.6252505>
24. Radford, A., Narasimhan, K.: Improving language understanding by generative pre-training (2018), <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:49313245>
25. Ramamurthy, R., Stenzel, R., Sifa, R., Ladi, A., Bauckhage, C.: Echo State Networks for Named Entity Recognition, pp. 110–120. *Artificial Neural Networks and Machine Learning – ICANN 2019: Workshop and Special Sessions* (2019)
26. Rogers, A., Hosur Ananthakrishna, S., Rumshisky, A.: What’s in your embedding, and how it predicts task performance. In: Bender, E.M., Derczynski, L., Isabelle, P. (eds.) *Proceedings of the 27th International Conference on Computational Linguistics*. pp. 2690–2703. Association for Computational Linguistics, Santa Fe, New Mexico, USA (Aug 2018)
27. Schaetti, N.: Behaviors of reservoir computing models for textual documents classification. In: *The 2019 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks* (07 2019)
28. Simov, K., Koprinkova-Hristova, P., Popov, A., Osenova, P.: Word embeddings improvement via echo state networks. In: *2019 IEEE International Symposium on INnovations in Intelligent SysTems and Applications (INISTA)* (2019)
29. Simov, K., Koprinkova-Hristova, P., Popov, A., et al.: A reservoir computing approach to word sense disambiguation. *Cognitive Computation* **15**, 1409–1418 (2023)
30. Team, G., Anil, R., Borgeaud, S., Alayrac, J.B., et al, J.Y.: Gemini: A family of highly capable multimodal models (2025), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2312.11805>
31. Tong, M.H., Bickett, A.D., Christiansen, E.M., Cottrell, G.W.: Learning grammatical structure with echo state networks. *Neural Networks* **20**(3), 424–432 (2007), echo State Networks and Liquid State Machines
32. Tortorella, D., Gallicchio, C., Micheli, A.: Hierarchical dynamics in deep echo state networks. In: Pimenidis, E., Angelov, P., Jayne, C., Papaleonidas, A., Aydin, M. (eds.) *Proceedings of the 31st International Conference on Artificial Neural Networks (ICANN 2022)*. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol. 13531 LNCS, pp. 668–679. Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-15934-3>
33. Ueda, R., Kuribayashi, T., Kando, S., Inui, K.: Syntactic learnability of echo state neural language models at scale (2025), <https://arxiv.org/abs/2503.01724>

34. Vaswani, A., Shazeer, N., Parmar, N., Uszkoreit, J., Jones, L., Gomez, A.N., Kaiser, L., Polosukhin, I.: Attention is all you need. In: NeurIPS 2017 (2017)
35. Verstraeten, D., Schrauwen, B., d'Haene, M., Stroobandt, D.: An experimental unification of reservoir computing methods. *Neural networks* **20**(3), 391–403 (2007)
36. Wang, H., Wang, Z., Du, M., Yang, F., Zhang, Z., Ding, S., Mardziel, P., Hu, X.: Score-cam: Score-weighted visual explanations for convolutional neural networks (2020), <https://arxiv.org/abs/1910.01279>
37. Yeruva, M., Reddy, J., Atmakuri, U., Marreddy, M.: Brain encoding using randomized recurrent networks. In: Proceedings of the 45th Annual Meeting of the Cognitive Science Society. vol. 45. Cognitive Science Society (2023)
38. Zhang, T., Yang, B.: An exact approach to ridge regression for big data. *Computational Statistics* **32**(3), 909–928 (2017)